

Analyzing the Potential of Wanito Sworo Newspaper to Foster Historical Practice Skills in Learning History of the Independent Curriculum through the Cats Strategy

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ABSTRACT: Newspapers have become a primary source for historians, with technological developments making newspapers digitized, offering easier access to data. So what if this document-based primary source is included in the realm of history learning? There is a lot of literature stating that learning history tends to be boring because it only consists of memorization and memory, but the offer related to the use of primary sources is worth considering. The integration of newspapers in history learning can use the CATS strategy (collect data, assess, think, tell stories). This research was conducted to examine the potential of newspapers published by Wanito Sworo in fostering practical history skills. This research aims to examine the potential of Wanito Sworo newspaper through the CATS (Collect, Assess, Thinking, Storytelling) strategy and see its effectiveness on historical practice skills. The historical documents or archives used can be used as a source of learning history. The research was conducted using library research with textbook analysis method. Using a literature review with the context analysis method is expected to build students' conceptual framework optimally.

KEYWORD: Newspaper, Wanito Sworo, History Learning CATS Strategy

INTRODUCTION

The image of history subjects among students is considered saturating. History learning is rote, uninteresting, and boring (Sayono, 2013). In fact, if examined further, history learning in the classroom can be more lively if educators use various strategies that are in accordance with the character, learning style of students, and learning objectives. Strategy is a planning method, or a series of activities designed to achieve certain educational goals (David, 1976). As stated in Permendikbud No. 8 of 2022, one of the objectives of learning history is to train skills in finding sources (heuristics), criticism and selection of sources (verification), analysis and synthesis of sources (interpretation), and writing history (historiography).

Primary source-based history learning is one of the issues emphasized in the Merdeka Curriculum (Djono, 2022). However, access to primary sources is quite difficult (Widiadi, et al., 2022). In fact, if in learning history educators can utilize archives or documents, it can renew students' interest in history. From here, various questions will arise from students such as what, who, how, when, and why an event can occur. The use of history learning resources in general needs to consider the relevance of learning resources to learning competencies and learning strategies that will be used (Handy, et al., 2022). In order to determine and use learning resources properly, teachers must understand the emphasis of material in each learning competency and be able to develop learning plans (Ibrahim, 2018). The use of diverse and relevant learning resources can help students in practicing practical historical skills, especially in the historical research section.

Why archives? Archives record events that have happened and those that have just happened. Kuswanto (2020) explained that archives can be regarded as an authentic and reliable source of information, so they contain fairly accurate information. Using the document utilization strategy, students will get a new atmosphere of learning history. Being directly involved in the process makes them learn like a historian. Many primary source documents can be used as learning resources, and to get them educators can utilize websites such as <https://www.delpher.nl/> or <https://archive.org/details/texts>.

One archive that has the potential to foster practical historical skills is the Wanito Sworo newspaper. During the colonial period, women were not free to access education. The colonial government paid almost no attention to educating the Javanese population (Meerkerk, 2019: 241). The difference in education obtained by each layer was felt by women. Women's lives during the colonial period were governed by traditions, rights and obligations of women who were considered inferior to men (Dewi & Gayung, 2014). During the colonial period, women did not receive education like men (Blackburn, 2004: 33). Education for boys tended to be more emphasized, because it would affect the economic and political fields, while education for women was legitimized in the socio-cultural field, which was not as broad in scope as the economic and political fields. Education for women is organized solely

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to maintain tradition and to educate the next generation, in other words, the division of labor between men and women is very different in society.

Wanito Sworo newspaper attempted to criticize the government through writing. It was established in 1913 in Brebes, Central Java. This newspaper began its publication in October 1912 and was edited by Raden Adjeng Sitti Soendari (Anon, 1914). Based on the situation and social conditions that surrounded women at that time, this newspaper tried to voice the issue of how to make women independent, able to determine their own destiny, and avoid early marriage. Other issues related to anti-polygamy, forced marriage, gender crimes, and the Women's Congress in Paris were also discussed (Mahayana, 2003). In order to explore the contents in the archive, the right strategy is needed for students to use.

A strategy that can be offered to support document-based learning is CATS. CATS consists of Collecting data, Assessing (review), Thinking, and Storytelling. In historical methodology, collecting data is similar to heuristic (source collection). Historical sources can be divided into two, namely written and unwritten (Kuntowijoyo, 2018: 73). The written document archive that will be reviewed in this article is the Wanito Sworo newspaper. Second, assess or review after obtaining the desired archive, students try to sort out which ones can be referred to as data and facts, then students provide interpretations and criticisms of these documents. The third stage is thinking, learners are given the opportunity to think about how an archive can be described into a narrative. Finally, storytelling, after being written, students can present their work in front of the class by telling stories. Through the utilization of newspapers in learning history and the use of the CATS strategy, it is hoped that students will be able to foster historical practice skills.

METHODS

This research aims to examine the potential of Wanito Sworo newspaper through the CATS (Collect, Assess, Thinking, Storytelling) strategy and see its effectiveness on historical practice skills. The historical documents or archives used can be used as a source of learning history. The research was conducted using library research with textbook analysis method. Rapid context analysis allows learners to build an optimal conceptual framework (Dick et al., 2015). Authentic learning experiences by analyzing newspapers can increase learning motivation, instructional relevance, and transfer of new knowledge and skills in learning (Brotowijoyo, 1991). Library research was used to gather relevant information. Context analysis was used to analyze the Wanito Sworo newspaper, what information was available, what form the newspaper took, and to critique whether this newspaper should be used as a primary source and learning resource for history.

RESULT AND DISCUSSIONS

History of Wanito Sworo Newspaper

In the 19th century women were placed in a disadvantaged position, they could not develop due to the dominance of men in a patriarchal culture. On the basis of biological differences between women and men, gender inequality occurs. Existing customs make it difficult for women to get their rights in social life (Maulidah, 2023). The current of modernization in the Dutch East Indies began to strengthen since the implementation of Ethical Politics. There were three programs implemented, namely education (educate), irrigation (irrigate), and transmigration (emigratie) (Ricklefs, 2008).

Educational opportunities gave rise to the existence of a modern elite or commonly known as the educated class. The emergence of this modern elite was the beginning of women's progress. The occurrence of changing times requires changes in the order of people's lives from traditional life to a more modern life (Rosana, 2015). So, it is hoped that there will be no more social layers based on human nature as a moral, intelligent, thinking and reasoning creature, women also have the right to develop all the capacities within themselves like what men get. This change began with the publication of the women's newspaper Wanito Sworo.

The Wanito Sworo newspaper was an early milestone in how women dared to voice their rights through the press. Edited by R.A Sitti Soendari, this newspaper was founded in 1913 in Brebes, Central Java. This newspaper started its publication in October 1912 and was edited by Raden Adjeng Sitti Soendari (Anon, 1914). At first, this magazine was published every month and printed in Kediri by the Boedi Karja printing house. Entering its third year, the newspaper was published biweekly. The format of the newspaper was in the form of a book with a size of 12 x 20 cm. Unfortunately, the print quality was not very good and there were too many misprints. Moreover, some articles often used Javanese, so they only reached the Central and East Java regions.

The contents in the Wanito Sworo rubric are Boeat Sekar Setaman: Chabar Redactie and Boenga Rampe, which contains short articles or writings from other media. With this rubrication arrangement, the number of pages of Wanito Sworo magazine ranged from 14-16 pages (Mahayana, 2003). In accordance with the mission "Kangge adjang kekosodan kawroeh" which means "As a forum for lack of knowledge", this newspaper aims to accommodate the exchange of ideas between women so as to produce new knowledge.

The content of this newspaper highlighted the downturn of women such as the lack of motivation to go to school, polygamy, and raised issues by comparing the condition of women in the Dutch East Indies with other countries such as Turkey (Wanito Sworo, 1914b) and Romania (Wanito Sworo, 1914a) In the magazine "Belang en Recht: Orgaan van het Comité tot Verbetering van den

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Maatschappelijken Rechtstoestand der Vrouw in Nederland, van den Vrouwenbond te Groningen en van de Vereeniging” Sitti Soendari as editor of Wanito Sworo wrote

“Javanese people will not be able to progress, if Javanese women remain stupid”. Sitti Soendari emphasized that women are not only teachers, but al so doctors for their children, therefore women must go to school and study hard.

Figure 1. Wanito Sworo newspaper

So emphatically this newspaper voiced that the position of women and men was equal. Although women have to go to school, according to Sitti Soendari, women must also have knowledge of cooking, sewing, batik, handicrafts, farming and everything related to the household. In a newspaper published in 1915, Wanito Sworo tried to compare the social conditions of native women with Western women. The moral courage of Javanese women who wanted to break traditions, customs and ways of life was so high. In the West, this kind of struggle was already very difficult and exhausting, while in Java women were bound a hundred times tighter by the troubled path of the past.

This newspaper thoroughly explores the concerns of women in 1913-1917. The history book published by Kemendikbudristek in 2021 has very little to say about the press. In chapter 2 with the title Indonesian National Movement, the discussion of the press is only about Soenting Melajoe and Poetri Hindia magazines. In fact, Wanito Sworo newspaper also has the potential to be explored

Figure 2. Newspaper discussing Siti Soedari
Source: De Preanger-bode, 1915

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further. Primarily, this newspaper was founded on the initiative of women, edited by women, and received letters and complaints. In addition, it can be used as Strengthening the Profile of Pancasila Students in the Independent Curriculum in the independent, critical reasoning, and creative sections.

Relevance of Newspapers as a History Learning Source

The advancement of technology has contributed new sources for historians that are presented in digital form. History learning cannot be separated from the history curriculum. The selection of history learning resources must automatically consider the desired competencies of the history curriculum. To find out the relevance of using the Wanito Sworo newspaper archive as a history learning resource, identification of learning materials is carried out based on the learning outcomes of history at the high school level in the Merdeka Curriculum. The relevance of using Wanito Sworo newspaper archives as a history learning resource can be seen from the following magazine.

Figure 3. Newspaper discussing Wanito Sworo

Source: De Expres, 1914

Material themes that are relevant to the content of news material in Wanito Sworo magazine include: 1) what is the role of national and regional figures in efforts to advance women's rights; 2) what is the meaning of gender equality; 3) what are the values of struggle shown by national figures; 4) what are the forms and strategies in fighting for the position of women. Based on this identification, it shows that Wanito Sworo newspaper has great potential to be used as a source of learning history. The use of newspaper archives as a source of learning history will help students to understand the spirit, ideas, and style of the struggle of female figures in advancing women.

The Potential of Newspapers in History Learning

History learning is an effort to shape character through affirmation and understanding of the superior values of a nation's journey. Learners today are expected to demonstrate skills and abilities that show they have not only mastered subject content but also the ability to put their learning into practice in real-life contexts (Pickford & Sally, 2006). Learners working in the practical domain often have to structure their own working lives in studios, laboratories or workplaces, so educators can encourage self-directed learning skills by incorporating them into assessed tasks. In historical practical skills, learners are expected to be able to read textbooks, reference books, and the internet; write and tell Indonesian history that is related or has a relationship with world history; process historical information non-digitally and digitally in various forms of historical applications, sound recordings, documentaries, photos, mock-ups, vlogs, timelines, story boards, infographics, videographics, comics, posters, and others (Permendikbud, 2022).

In history learning, historical practice skills are included in the knowledge content of the Merdeka Curriculum for Phase-E and Phase-F History subjects. Practical skills have at least several indicators that must be met such as critically reflective practice. Critical reflection practice is a process that can make learners develop greater self-awareness and change the way they see themselves in relation to practice, broader social issues, questions of ethics and interpersonal relationships (Maidment, et al., 2023). Engaging in critical reflection also entails thinking about how practice relates to theory and considering how theory, in turn, can be reshaped to reflect contemporary and changing social contexts. Therefore, in the context of learning history, critical reflection can be understood as a form of self-reflection of historical material that discusses the past, for future improvement.

History is not only something that discusses political and military issues, but the use of newspapers in learning is no less important. Traditionally, newspapers are used for tasks such as creating general outlines, facts and trends; seeking descriptions or details about people, places and events (Allen & Sieczkiewicz, 2010). Rules of thumb for effective newspaper searches have been

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proposed (a) Make a list; (b) Look for some kind of common thread; (c) Don't just use one newspaper; (d) Don't fall into the trap of only reading articles that match the keywords you are looking for; (e) Use existing secondary literature; (f) Take very thorough notes; and (g) Don't ignore letters and advertisements (Rachel, 2009). These stages can be incorporated into history learning if supported by more up-to-date strategies.

This research offers a new strategy to foster practical history skills, namely using the CATS (Collecting data, Assessing, Thinking, Storytelling) strategy based on documents or archives. Collecting data is the stage to generate data relevant to the research topic (Dick et al., 2015). Data collection is a valuable tool for uncovering knowledge and making informed decisions. By understanding different methods and considering important factors, learners can collect accurate data from Wanito Sworo newspaper, making it useful for learning purposes. Furthermore, assessing and thinking, this stage is used by students to sort out which data and facts are included in the Wanito Sworo newspaper. This sorting is done based on the type of information contained in the newspaper. After that, students narrate the data and facts that have been obtained, assisted by other secondary sources. So that the narrative presented can be held accountable for its credibility.

Storytelling dates back to prehistoric times, storytelling has been an important part of thousands of cultures for thousands of years (Wardiah, 2017). Humans tell stories as a means of entertainment, communication, and passing on information from generation to generation. The tradition of storytelling is an ancient art form that is woven into the fabric of human culture (Yılmaz & Cığerci, 2018). Its centrality to the human experience makes the ability to tell a good story an invaluable art and skill; equal parts inspiration, craftsmanship, and artistry. In this stage, learners who have compiled a narrative can share their experiences during the composing process and the results obtained. This activity can accommodate learners with kinesthetic learning styles. The steps of the CATS strategy that the researcher tried to develop:

Sintaks of CATS	Educator activities	Student activity
Collecting data	Educators condition their students to be ready for learning. Educators provide website links to access archives.	Learners are encouraged to search and sort the data obtained, then formulate questions based on the educator's instructions.
Assess the data that has been obtained (Assess)	Educators guide and facilitate learners to conduct internal and external criticism.	Learners determine which data can be used as facts and only as data, according to topics relevant to their study.
Give an opinion on the data that has been assessed (Thinking)	Educator facilitates learners by giving some questions	Learners answer the questions presented, then organize them into a narrative
Telling the results of the report (Storytelling)	Educator gives feedback on students' work	Learners tell the process of preparing the narrative and the information that has been obtained.

This strategy is suitable for learners with kinesthetic learning styles. They can directly analyze the data presented, sort it out, then write and tell it in front of the class. The CATS strategy seeks to accommodate the needs of learners so that they no longer feel that learning history is boring. This kind of direct involvement will generate more curiosity from students.

CONCLUSIONS

The utilization of newspapers in history learning can eliminate the image of history subjects that are considered boring among students. Directly involving students in the action of collecting data, assessing, thinking, and storytelling provides another meaning related to learning history. It is as if students will become historians who are able to narrate an event. Although access to newspapers is quite difficult, there are several websites that can accommodate the needs of students. One of the newspapers used in this research is Wanito Sworo, this newspaper explores the needs and rights of women to be equal to men. Through newspapers, Wanito Sworo strives for women's voices and criticisms to be heard. Such is the rigor of their efforts, but it is still not too much discussed in the history teaching module published by the Ministry of Education and Culture. So, the researchers hope that newspapers or press published by women will begin to be explored further to enrich the treasure of knowledge of women's history.

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